

STAY HEALTHY: SIMPLE EXERCISES FOR SENIORS

For Wellness Elevated Clients

MARCHING IN PLACE

- Stand tall with your feet hip-width apart.
- Lift your knees one at a time as if marching, swinging your arms for balance.
- Keep going for 1-2 minutes, rest if needed under marching in place.

WALL PUSH-UPS

- Stand facing a wall, about arm's length away.
- Place your hands on the wall at shoulder height.
- Bend your elbows to bring your chest toward the wall, then push back to start. Repeat 10-15 times.

SEATED BEND

- Extend one leg straight out, keeping the other foot on the ground.
- Slowly reach toward your toes and hold the stretch for 15-30 seconds. Switch legs.

STANDING ON 1 LEG

- Stand behind a sturdy chair and hold onto it for support.
- Lift one foot off the ground and balance on the other leg for 10-15 seconds.
- Switch legs and repeat. Try to increase your balance time as you get better.

CONSULT A HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONAL BEFORE STARTING ANY NEW EXERCISE ROUTINE."

